

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Object

Risma Paper Analysis For *Dinamika Psikologi Di Dalam Film "Ku Kira Kau Rumah"*

Background and Analysis

Perancangan ini bertujuan untuk memberikan gambaran kepada remaja tentang risiko gangguan bipolar agar mereka lebih peka terhadap gangguan bipolar (bipolar disorder). Saya sering bertemu dengan orang yang mengalami gangguan jiwa karena berbagai faktor. Ketika dibiarkan tanpa pengawasan, ada situasi sosial dan ekonomi yang akan segera terjadi yang mengarah ke masalah yang lebih buruk: penyakit mental. Kebanyakan orang, dan mungkin semua orang, mengalami depresi, tetapi perilaku ini dianggap normal dalam situasi tertentu (seperti putus cinta). Orang dengan gangguan mood merasa sakit dan mengganggu kehidupan penderita gangguan mood (gangguan mood). Salah satu gangguan mood swing adalah bipolar, gangguan ini melibatkan depresi. Remaja sekarang cenderung labil, Siswa yang masih dalam kategori remaja sangat praktis untuk mengubah pola pikir, sikap dan suasana hati, karena rata-rata mereka masih labil dalam beberapa hal sehingga sangat praktis untuk mengalami depresi.

Dikatakan bahwa jika dapat menjaga stabilitas emosi, akan pulih dari gangguan bipolar sehingga tidak terlalu tinggi selama mania dan tidak terlalu rendah selama satu fase depresi. Proses pemulihan Niskala memakan waktu usang dan tak akan pernah berakhir. Niskala mengalami kekambuhan bahkan sempat dianggap bunuh diri. Faktor internal yang membantu proses pemulihan adalah memahami penyakit yang dideritanya. Pengetahuan buku dalam dunia perkuliahan berarti, mereka dapat lebih mengenali kecacatan mereka sendiri dan mencegah kemungkinan terulang kembali.

Faktor eksternal yang membantu proses pemulihan antara lain peran keluarga, peran teman, peran pasangan, dan juga peran narkoba. Bentuk dukungan yang paling umum dukungan emosional dan informatif. Dalam Niskala, yg berguna meredakan emosi ialah sosok pasangan yang mengalami kesepian dan peran Ibu Niskala yang selalu mengerti apa yang diinginkan Niskala. Itu membuka matanya bahwa banyak yang mencintai dan merawatnya.

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Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,

Iya tersedia data ataupun informasi terkait dinamika psikologi di dalam film” ku kira kau rumah”

2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

Iya, data dan informasi di dapatkan melalui observasi setiap adegan yang terdapat di dalam film ,wawancara di dapatkan dari orang-orang sekitar atau yang mengalami gangguan psikologi seperti film tersebut, serta dokumentasi.

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

Menurut saya, penelitian ini sudah melakukan pengecekan plagiatisme dan sudah memenuhi syarat.

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

Tidak, karena penelitian ini cenderung berkontribusi dalam masalah kehidupan seseorang yang mengalami bipolar.

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

Menurut saya iya , karena persoalan kehidupan di era anak remaja sedang ramai terjadi dan sering kali menyangkut dengan masalah gangguan mood.

6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and

Iya, karena permasalahan gangguan mood sangat penting dan harus segera mendapatkan solusi sehingga tidak akan terlalu banyak lagi yang mengalami gangguan mood. Karena di kehidupan sekarang banyak sekali anak remaja yang sudah mengalami gangguan mood.

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7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

Menurut saya tidak , karena penelitian ini tidak sesuai dengan bidang studi yang di pilih.

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

Semakin banyak mahasiswa yang mengantisipasi diri nya untuk tidak terlalu depresi akan hal-hal yang tidak penting untuk dipikirkan sehingga yang mengalami gangguan mood akan berkurang, serta banyak juga yang saling menguatkan satu sama lain agar tetap menjalankan kehidupannya.

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

Menurut saya, penelitian ini bermanfaat untuk lebih bisa mengontrol emosi dan mengerti satu sama lain/sesama makhluk sosial.

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